

**Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership**

YewMaker

Roadmapping the Transition to Digital Medicines Information

Roundtable Report
Feb 2022

Contents

- [SMP overview](#) [Page 3-6](#)
- [Roundtable](#) [Page 7-24](#)
 - [Structure](#) [Page 8-9](#)
 - [Background](#) [Page 10-14](#)
 - [Innovations](#) [Page 15-18](#)
 - [Takeaways](#) [Page 19-23](#)
 - [Feedback](#) [Page 24](#)
- [Next steps](#) [Page 25-26](#)
- [References](#) [Page 27](#)
- [Contact us](#) [Page 28](#)

4.5 Trillion medicines made every year ¹

But:

- Billions of effective medicines discarded unused ^{2,3}
- Billions of medicines lost due to packaging or delivery failures ^{4,5}
- Huge environmental cost - 25% healthcare CO2e in medicines ²⁻⁷
- Huge financial cost - \$billions wasted every year ²⁻⁷
- Two billion people do not have access to basic medicines ⁸

Solutions require collective stewardship, commitment, and action.

Sustainable Medicines Partnership

A multi-stakeholder global partnership executing a programme to build, test & scale sustainable medicines frameworks and solutions.

**Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership**

Concept	2020
Programme design	2021
Programme delivery	2022-2025
Solutions scaled	2026-2030

SMP Programme

Four year programme to deliver science-based, scalable solutions through integrated Projects.

SMP Projects:

- Target 6 pillars of sustainable medicines.
- Deliver data-driven solutions.
- Deliver sector-wide frameworks.
- Deliver standards and metrics.
- Deliver implementation toolkits.

SPECIFIC

We build sustainable solutions through sector-wide collaborative action

SYSTEMIC

We build the data, frameworks, and standards required for policy change

Pillars of Sustainable Medicines

SMP Roundtable

**Roadmapping the
transition to digital
medicines information**

18th November 2021

Roundtable structure

**Sector-wide
participation**

**43 participants across
whole community**

**Innovation
presentations**

**Cutting-edge
content**

**Small & large
group discussion**

**Structured so every
voice heard**

Roundtable participants

Roundtable Poll: individuals identified themselves as part of one or more of the SMP stakeholder groups.

Roadmapping the transition to digital medicines information

Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership

Background

Medicines Information - current landscape

Complex with high regional variability
Mixed professional, patient, and product information

Information for Professionals

Digital in most territories
US is an exception
~30+ pages

Information for Patients

Printed in most territories
Not patient-centred
~4-7 pages (normal font)

Why Change - Patients

Research shows current leaflets are: ⁹⁻¹³

- Hard to read: small font, complex language
- Hard to search: for relevant content
- Hard to update: impacting patient safety
- Hard to adapt: to different platforms / patients
- Hard to access: content lost, if leaflet lost

Medicines information must better serve patient needs

Why Change - Planet

>100 Billion paper leaflets produced / year.

- Require huge quantities of trees, water, energy
- 20% are never packed, for multiple reasons
- Increase size, weight, and storage requirements
- Increase transport requirements
- Generate ~500,000 tonnes CO₂e / year

100B leaflets needs: ¹⁴

9 million trees

H₂O = fill Sydney harbour 4 times

Energy = fuel 50,000 homes for a year

Paper is a valuable resource that should never be wasted

Why Change - Business

Paper leaflets impact medicines manufacture:

- 10% machinery downtime due to leaflet issues
- Add ~6 months to lead time
- Market specificity limits supply flexibility
- Repetitive bulk manual handling for employees
- Leaflet changes add delays and waste

Paper leaflets cause delays and waste of medicines

**Roadmapping the
transition to digital
medicines information**

**Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership**

Innovations

Innovations - Policy

The Therapeutic Products Branch (TPB) finalized guidance on e-labelling of therapeutic products (TPs) in Singapore has been published and will take effect from 30 April 2021. As part of HSA's calibrated approach, only prescription-only medicines will be eligible for e-labelling.

E-PIL
Belgium & Luxembourg
Pioneer Pilot Project

BALTIC REGULATORY AGENCIES ANNOUNCE THE EPIL PROJECT FOR HOSPITAL USE MEDICINES

Notice: Product Monograph Implementation Plans

May 12, 2020

Our Reference No: 19-123473-315

Electronic product information for human medicines in the EU: key principles

A joint EMA-HMA-EC collaboration

Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Safety Information

No. 381 March 2021

Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare & Pharmaceutical Safety and Environmental Health Bureau,
Labour and Welfare, Japan

Many health systems are trialling digital medicines information¹⁵

Innovations - Content

MyRx.tv

Your Medications Explained

Watch videos about your medication

myHealthbox

better information for better health

Pharmacy .nl

All about medicines. Reliable information from the pharmacist.

 U.S. NATIONAL LIBRARY OF MEDICINE

RAVIMIAMET **Ravimiregister**

FASS **Allmänhet**

To the homepage

Digital content (text, audio, video) is increasingly available¹⁶

Innovations - Access

myHealthbox APIs

First Databank's Authoritative Drug Information Helps Answer Customer Questions on Amazon Alexa

Specialized answers about medication information were created specifically for voice-enabled service

Many ways to access digital content are becoming available¹⁷

**Roadmapping the
transition to digital
medicines information**

**Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership**

Roundtable Takeaways

Top 3 takeaways

Patients First

Patient need and safety should be the primary determinant of information content and access.

Implementation by Integration

Data from existing research, pilots, real world evidence should be integrated to deliver change.

Digital by 2025

Digital medicines information should be the default mode of communication by 2025.

Patients First

Medicines information:

- **Simpler content:** to increase understanding & adherence
- **Multimedia formats:** to increase accessibility
- **Multilingual:** to increase accessibility
- **Dynamic & always up-to-date:** to increase safety
- **Structured & searchable:** to improve user experience
- **Linked as standard:** to other formats and information

Patient need & safety should determine content and access

Additional information should be readily available as required

Implementation by Integration

Broad consensus on digital transition principles:

- **Manufacturers:** many product-specific pilots
- **Health professionals:** many supportive research studies
- **Patients:** studies all show need for improvement
- **Health systems:** several already on digital roadmap
- **Policymakers:** many recommend digital transition

Integration of the abundance of data & research can provide an evidence-based digital implementation roadmap

Digital by 2025

Digital information:

- is flexible, accessible, dynamic, inter-operable
- can be accessed in different ways and formats
- is already used by most professionals and citizens
- requires much less natural resource to produce
- will reduce stock loss and medicines waste

Roundtable Poll: 67% believed digital medicines information should be the default by 2025, 100% by 2030.

Digital medicines information should be the primary format by 2025

Alternatives should be readily available as required

Roundtable feedback

Good background on the scale of the problem and the issues faced in packaging. Useful to hear different viewpoints and the obstacles that need to be overcome.

People with different background and perspectives working towards the same goal.

Multi-stakeholder and experienced panel. Useful sharing of initiatives from other markets.

Great structure and pace. Very much liked the focus on not presupposing the problem space, but drawing that out from the groups.

Helpful to make connections across wider groups.

Great small group discussions. All perspectives honored and included.

Efficient way to gather information - learnt a lot.

100% of survey respondents found the Roundtable useful

**Roadmapping the
transition to digital
medicines information**

**Sustainable
Medicines
Partnership**

Next Steps

SMP Project - Digitising medicines information

'One-Page' essential content

Patient-centred, interoperable, standardised, core content.¹⁸

Prototype 'digital-first'

Hospital medicines: leaflets are not given to hospital patients, digital can be the default.

Implementation frameworks

Integrate research and real world data to build digital transition roadmaps.

References

1. [Global Medicines Use in 2020](#)
2. [Expired Medication: societal, regulatory and ethical aspects of a wasted opportunity](#)
3. [Evaluation of the scale, causes and costs of waste medicines](#)
4. [Failures in temperature-controlled logistics cost biopharma industry billions](#)
5. [Ensuring a safe and robust supply of pharma materials](#)
6. [A carbon footprint assessment of the NHS](#)
7. [The role of material efficiency in environmental stewardship](#)
8. [Access to Medicine Foundation - Worldwide 5 billion people have access to medicine](#)
9. [From print to screen: regulatory considerations to adopting innovative approaches to patient information](#)
10. [Provision and need for medicine information in Asia and Africa](#)
11. [Readability of medicinal package leaflets: a systematic review](#)
12. [Advancing best practices for prescription drug labeling](#)
13. [Protecting seniors from medication labelling mistakes](#)
14. Extrapolated from AstraZeneca internal data
15. Policy Innovations - each image is a hyperlink to reference
16. Content Innovations - each image is a hyperlink to reference
17. Access Innovations - each image is a hyperlink to reference
18. [The science of communicating medication information to consumers](#)

Contact us

If you would like to be involved email: info@yewmaker.com

Read more about YewMaker and the SMP: <https://www.yewmaker.com/>

Follow us:

Twitter [@YewMaker](https://twitter.com/YewMaker)

LinkedIn [YewMaker](https://www.linkedin.com/company/yewmaker)

We thank all participants for their energetic and
constructive engagement

Cite as: Rahman, N., & Mahamdallie, S. (2022). Roadmapping the Transition to Digital Medicines Information - Roundtable Report. YewMaker. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19051958>.

Content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license ([CC BY](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)), by YewMaker.